

CORRELATING LA MUSEUM VISITORS TO CRIMES IN LA

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1 Data Summary

In this experiment, This data management plan provides assistance and clarification of the process of testing the correlation between numbers of museums visitors' city and numbers of crimes in Los Angeles..

With this purpose, the following datasets are required:

LA crime data from 2010 to present,LA museum visitors.

The information contained is in en language formatted as CSV. About if there is sensitive data, the answer would be No. And for personal data, the answer would be No. This dataset has been issued on: 2019-12-31T00:00:00.

2.1 Making data FAIR

1- LA crime data from 2010 to present has the next keywords:

To have a better understanding of the data, the following Metadata has been generated:

DublinCore

This data is published in type of CSV. This data set is distributed under license: unknown

2- LA museum visitors has the next keywords:

To have a better understanding of the data, the following Metadata has been generated:

DublinCore

This data is published in type of CSV. This data set is distributed under license: unknown

3 Allocation of resources

1- Costs and potential value of long term preservation.

Even for the long-term preservation, it is stated on Zenodo that even for future data migration, the DOIs will stay working just as fine according to the same subscription plan.. The cost was to match requirements of Zenodo

4 Data Security

There is no information regarding security issues.

5 Ethical aspects

To be covered in the context of the ethics review, ethics section of DoA and ethics deliverables.

Include references and related technical aspects if not covered by the former. Input data and the generated data content were completely anonymized, so with that being preserved on Zenodo, there will be no unethical act.

6 Other issues

There are no Other aspects related.